

Release management of production-quality middleware components

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Grid middleware distributions are often large software artifacts, which include a set of components each providing a basic functionality, e.g. data storage, authentication and authorization, resource monitoring, and job management. The European Middleware Initiative (EMI) is a collaboration of the three major middleware providers in Europe (ARC, gLite and UNICORE) and other consortia which aims to deliver a consolidated set of middleware components for deployment in existing distributed computing infrastructures strengthening the reliability of the services and establishing a sustainable model to maintain and evolve the middleware. To release software components satisfying these requirements it has been chosen the Product Team (PT) model.

The PTs are small teams of software engineers responsible for the release of a specific software product fulfilling both the technical requirements of robustness, reliability, integration and the user communities requirements. The gLite Job Management PT is responsible for the gLite Computing Element (CREAM CE) a job management web-service to submit, manage and monitor computational jobs to a Local Resource Management System and for the gLite Workload Management System (WMS), a service meant to provide reliable and efficient distribution and management of end-user requests in terms of both computing and data. To efficiently release CREAM CE and WMS the job management PT has defined precise processes and procedures for the testing and certification chain and dedicated ad hoc testbeds.

Software testing and certification testbeds

Test and certification of job management PT software components are managed exploiting two dedicated testbeds:

Scopes:

- Used for preliminary tests on a release candidate. Update/installation and configuration procedures are tested. Integration and functionality tests are performed.
- Used for tests on backward compatibility and regression tests using test suites

Scopes:

- Used to simulate a production environment various, distributed, with more users and VOs involved
- Used to test robustness with high load for long time

Software quality control flow

Software quality control chain begins when a software component ready to be tested.

First step: deployment on testbed A

- installation and configuration from scratch on dedicated machines
- update of part of the testbed to test update procedures
- update of release documentation
- first bunch of functionality tests
- run of a test suite to perform regression tests and to check backward compatibility

Second step: deployment on testbed B

- update of the testbed (installation and configuration using tested procedures)
- run of a short test of production simulation to check functionality and resource usage.
- run of a longer test with higher load.

Third step: release in production.

The described test/certification environment has been useful also to underline weakness of the tested software component in terms of both functionality and robustness.

Acronyms:

UI	User Interface	LSF	Load Sharing Facility
WN	Worker Node	PBS	Portable Batch System
LB	Logging and Bookkeeping		
BDII	Berkley Database Information Index		
VO	Virtual Organization		